

Preparation of Pineapple Wine and Study on Some Physical Parameters in the Fruit of *Ananas comosus* (L.) Merr. (Nar Nut)

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Abstract

Preliminary phytochemical screening of selected sample was done by test tube method. According to these tests, *Ananas comosus* (L.) Merr. (Pineapple) juice contains glycosides, phenolic compounds, carbohydrates, reducing sugars, alkaloids, α - amino acids, flavonoids, terpenoids, polyphenols, steroids, saponins and tannins while pineapple wine does not contain reducing sugars, carbohydrates and steroids. Moreover, the carbohydrate content (15.84%) was determined by Lane and Eynon's method. In addition, the functional groups containing in the fruit of *Ananas comosus* (L.) Merr., pineapple wine was determined by FT IR spectra data. Furthermore, some physicochemical parameters in the fruit of the *Ananas comosus* (L.) Merr., pineapple wine were measured such as specific gravity (1.0048 %), alcohol strength (6 %), acidity (0.15 %), total solid (2.09 %), pH (4.61), light yellow color, pineapple bouquet flavor were present respectively.

Keywords: *Ananas comosus* (L.) Merr., pineapple, Phytochemical constituents, Carbohydrate content, Physicochemical parameters, FT IR

Introduction

Ananas comosus (L.) Merr., pineapple is a perennial herb plant. It is one of the most important commercial fruit in the world. *Ananas comosus* (L.) Merr., pineapple is an important source of sugars, organic acids, vitamins and some essential minerals for human nutrition and its good flavor, aroma, juiciness and sweetness is known and appreciated by consumers (Pineapple production, 2016).

Pineapple wine is the most well-known. The stage of fermentation is fairly easy to achieve due to all the sugar in the fruits. The principal carbohydrate, sugar in fruit juice is soluble sugar. Wine can be made by direct fermentation of the fruit juice by yeasts. Wine is any alcoholic beverage produced from juices of variety of fruits by fermentative action of microorganisms either spontaneously or seeding with a particular strain mainly of yeast species to adopt a particular quality of wine. Wine is one of the most recognizable high value added products from fruits. So, it can be used for drinking at any time, fermented fruit juices are made in Hawaii. It is also made in Nigeria by Jacobs Wines, in Okinawa, Japan from local produce for many years (Duke, J. A. *et al.*, 1981). Wine has been produced for thousands of years. Wine has long played an important role in religion (Robinson, J., 2006).

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Materials and Methods

Preparation of *Ananas comosus* (L.) Merr. (Pineapple) Wine

Ripe and undamaged fruits of *Ananas comosus* (L.) Merr. (Pineapple), used for phytochemical investigation and wine fermentation were purchased from Myot Thit Market, Pyay Township, Bago region. The ripe pineapple fruits were washed with distilled water to remove impurities and sliced of the shell. For the preparation of pineapple wine, small pieces of pineapple placed into the blender. The result pineapple juices were filtered through cotton filter to remove pineapple pulp. The filtrate juice was used for fermentation to produce wine.

Flow Sheet for Wine Making Process of the Fruit of *Ananas comosus* (L.) Merr.

Wine Making Procedure of the Fruit of *Ananas comosus* (L.) Merr.

Ripe and undamaged fruits of *Ananas comosus* (L.) Merr. were washed well with distilled water and crushed. Before fermentation, clean and fresh fruits of pineapple were pressed with heavier pressure to get the pineapple juice. This pineapple juices were combined and its volume was measured. Sodium metabisulphite solution, prepared by dissolving 0.3 g of

$\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_5$ crystal in 650 ml of distilled warm water was added to the combined pineapple juice with stirring. After being added sodium metabisulphite, the must obtained was sit for 2 hours at room temperature. Then, the must was filtered through cotton filter to remove pineapple skins. When the brix was less than 21 °C, pH of pineapple juice (filtrate) was 3.5- 4.5 and the temperature of it was maintained at 21- 25 °C (room temperature), sugar was added to this filtrate. 8 g yeast was added to 200 mL of warm water and set aside for 10 minutes before adding to the filtrate. Then, yeast solution was added to the pineapple juice in the fermenter. At the same time, 0.1 g of ammonium phosphate and 100 mL of distilled water were also added to the juice. The fermenter was covered to prevent air and sunlight. Fermentation was allowed at room temperature in anaerobic condition. As soon as fermentation started, bubbles can be seen in it. The temperature of the solution increased. So, to resist the heat of fermentation, two third of the fermenter was dipped in the cold water to maintain the desired temperature of about (20-28 °C). Fermentation was allowed to continue for three weeks at the dark place. After three weeks, decantation of turbid wine was rapidly carried out to remove sediment including death yeast cells and other impurities. Decantation was repeated at every one week to get desired clarity of wine. After fermentation, wine was stabilized and aging of wine was allowed in the dark for at least three months. Then, a little sodium metabisulphite solution (0.1g in 100 mL) was added to wine just before bottling to ensure the absence of microorganisms. Then wine was stored in brown bottle for many years before drinking.

Phytochemical Screening of Pineapple Juice and Pineapple Wine

The types of chemical compounds present in the sample were determined by preliminary phytochemical tests using with appropriate reagents. Therefore, phytochemical tests were done on the *Ananas comosus* (L.) Merr. with a view to determine the presence or absence of alkaloids, glycosides, carbohydrates, phenolic compounds, α -amino acids, flavonoids, steroids, tannins, terpenoids, saponins, reducing sugars and polyphenols. Thus, the sugars from pineapple ripe fruit juice have already converted to ethyl alcohol in fermentation process during wine making.

Detection of Carbohydrate Content in Pineapple Juice by Lane & Eynon's Method

10 g of pineapple juice and 125 cm³ of 0.675 M sulphuric acid were added into a round bottomed flask. The solution was refluxed in water- bath for about 10 hours. At the end of the hydrolysis, the contents were filtered off and calcium hydroxide was added to it until the pH of solution reaches to pH 6.5. The precipitate calcium sulphate was removed by filtration and washing with distilled water. The filtrate was passed through Amberlite IR-120 resin to remove the cation up negative to Molish's test. The solutions were concentrated and reduced to 100 cm³ in a volumetric flask. The hydrolyzate were titrated with standard Fehling's solution to determine the glucose content (Vogel, A.I., 1956).

Determination of Physical Parameters in Pineapple Wine

Physical parameters such as color, alcohol strength, acidity, total solid and specific gravity, sugar content, pH of pineapple wine were measured at Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Irrigation Small Scale Industries Department, Yangon.

Study on FT IR Spectroscopy in Pineapple Wine

Fourier-transform Infrared spectroscopy (FT IR) is a technique used to obtain an infrared spectrum of absorption or emission of a solid, liquid or gas. The functional groups containing in pineapple wine were determined by FT IR spectroscopic method (FIMLS, 2016). The infrared spectra of the fruit of pineapple wine were recorded on a Shimadzu Perkin Elmer Spectrum GX FT IR spectrophotometer at Universities' Research Center, University of Yangon.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 Preliminary Phytochemical Test for Pineapple Juice and Pineapple Wine

No	Type of Compounds	Test reagent	Pineapple Juice		Pineapple Wine	
			Observation	Remark	Observation	Remark
1	Glycosides	10% lead acetate	white ppt.	+	white ppt.	+
2	Reducing sugars	NaOH, Benedict's solution	orange red ppt.	+	no red ppt.	-
3	Phenolic compounds	10% FeCl ₃	deep blue color	+	greenish yellow	+
4	Carbohydrates	10% α-naphthol, 1.25% conc. H ₂ SO ₄	red ring	+	no red ring	-
5	Flavonoids	conc.HCl, Mg turning	pale pink color	+	pale yellow	+
6	Saponins	-	frothing	+	frothing	+
7	Alkaloids	Dragendroff's reagent	orange ppt.	+	yellow ppt.	+
8	Polyphenols	1% K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆ , 1% FeCl ₃	greenish blue color	+	greenish blue	+
9	Steroids	acetic nhydride, pet ether, 1.25% conc. H ₂ SO ₄	green color	+	no green color	-
10	Terpenoids	acetic anhydride, chloroform 1.25% conc: H ₂ SO ₄	pink color	+	pink color	+
11	Tannins	dil. H ₂ SO ₄ , 10% FeCl ₃	Yellowish brown ppt.	+	greenish brown ppt.	+
12	α-Amino acids	Ninhydrin reagent	purple spot	+	purple spot	+
(+) = presence (-) = absence (ppt.) = precipitate						

Table 2 Carbohydrate Content in Pineapple Juice by Lane & Eynon's Technique

Content	Results	Literature values
Carbohydrates	15.84%	13%

Table 3 Results of Some Physicochemical Parameters in Pineapple Wine

No	Pineapple wine	Results	Literature values
1	Specific gravity	1.0048	0.998
2	Total solid (%)	2.09	1.81
3	Acidity (% as Citric acid)	0.15	0.090
4	Alcohol strength (%)	6	8
5	Sugar content (% as Brix)	2	3.6
6	pH	4.61	3.5
7	Color (at 400 nm)	Light Yellow (0.416A)	Light yellow
8	Flavor	Pineapple bouquet	Pineapple bouquet

Table 4 FT IR Assignments in Pineapple Wine

No	Wave number (cm^{-1})		Possible Assignments
	Observed Value	Literature Value	
1	3303.44	3550 - 3200 (strong, broad)	O-H stretching vibration of alcoholic group and acid group
2	1635.02	1650 - 1550 (medium)	C=O stretching vibration of acid group C=C stretching vibration of alkene or conjugated alkene group
3	1045.30	1075 - 1020	C-O stretching vibration

Figure 1 FT IR spectrum in pineapple wine

Conclusion

The preliminary phytochemical tests revealed the presence of alkaloids, glycosides, carbohydrates, α -amino acids, flavonoids, steroids, tannins, terpenoids, saponins, reducing sugars, polyphenols and phenolic compounds in the pineapple juice sample while pineapple wine does not contain reducing sugars, carbohydrates and steroids. And then, carbohydrate content in the pineapple juice was found 15.84%. Some physicochemical parameters of pineapple wine such as specific gravity (1.0048 %), alcohol strength (6 %), acidity (0.15 %), total solid (2.09 %), pH (4.61), light yellow color, pineapple bouquet flavor were observed. In addition, identification of the functional groups was determined by FT IR technique. According to FT IR spectral data, the pineapple wine sample contained the alcoholic group and acid group. *Ananas comosus* (L.) Merr., pineapple wine has distinctive tangy taste and also has high medicinal value. Therefore, preparation of *Ananas comosus* (L.) Merr., pineapple wine is simple, cost effective, valuable diet and benefits for health to consumers.

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References

- Alvarenga, L.M. (2015). "Analysis of alcoholic fermentation of pulp and residues from Pineapple processing". *Journal of food*, **13**(1), 11.
- Anbuselvi. S and Hemalatha. R. (2013). "Physical chemical constituents of pineapple pulp and waste". *Journal of chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, **5**(2), 241.
- Duke, J. A. and K. K. Wain. (1981). *Medicinal Plants of the world*. Computer index with more than 85,000 entries. **3**.
- Harbone, J.B. (1984). "Phytochemical Methods". *A Guide to Modern Techniques of Plant Analysis*, 2nd Edition, Chapman and Hall Ltd., USA.
- Pineapple production. (2016). "Crops/Regions/World List/Production Quantity", UN food and Agriculture Organization, Corporation Statistical Database (FAOSTAT). 2017. Retrieved 27 February 2018.
- Robinson, J., (2006). *The Oxford Companion of wine*, 3rd Edition, Oxford University press, 268-280.
- Tin Wa, MSc. (1972). "Phytochemical Screening Method and Procedures". *Phytochemical Bulletin of Botanical Society of America*, Ins., **5**(3), 4-10.
- Vogel, A.I. (1956). "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry". English Language Book Society and Longman Group Ltd., London, 454 .
- Vogel, A.L. (1966). "Qualitative Organic Analysis". London: 2nd Ed, Longman, William and Sons Ltd., London, 2nd Ed.
- Zoecklein, B.W., Y. Jasinski and H. Mc Mahan. (1988). "Effect of Fermentation, Ageing and Ageing Sur Lie on Total and Phenol-free Riesling (*Vitis-vinifera* L.) Glycosides". *J. Food Composition and Analysis*, **11**, 240-248.